

Statistical properties of superflares on solar-type stars with Kepler data

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Superflares are flares that release total energy 10^4 times greater than that of the biggest solar flares with energy of $\sim 10^{32}$ erg. We searched superflares on solar-type stars (G-type main sequence stars) using the Kepler 1-min and 30-min cadence data. We found 187 superflares on 23 stars from 1-min cadence data (Q0-17) and more than 1500 superflares on 279 stars from 30-min cadence data (Q0-6) (Maehara+2012, Nature; Shibayama+2013, ApJS; Maehara+2015, EP&S). The bolometric energy of detected superflares ranges from the order of 10^{32} to 10^{36} erg. Using these data, we found that the occurrence frequency (dN/dE) of superflares is expressed as a power-law function of flare energy (E) with the index of -1.5 for $10^{33} < E < 10^{36}$ erg.

Most of the superflare stars show quasi-periodic light variations with the amplitude of a few percent, which can be explained by the rotation of the star with large starspots (Notsu+2013 ApJ). The bolometric energy released by flares is consistent with the magnetic energy stored around such large starspots. Furthermore, our analyses indicate that the occurrence frequency of superflares depends on the rotation period, and that the flare frequency increases as the rotation period decreases. However, the energy of the largest flares observed in a given period bin does not show any clear correlation with the rotation period (Notsu+2013, ApJ). We also found that the duration of superflares increases with the flare energy as $E^{0.39 \pm 0.03}$ (Maehara+2015, EP&S). This can be explained if we assume the time-scale of flares is determined by the Alfvén time.

1. Solar flares and "Superflares"

- Solar flares are energetic explosions in the solar atmosphere (corona).
 - Solar flares are caused by the sudden release of magnetic energy stored near sunspots.
- Typical energy released by solar flares: $10^{29} \sim 10^{32}$ erg
- Occurrence frequency (dN/dE) decreases as the flare energy (E) increases.
 - Power-law distribution: $dN/dE \propto E^{-\alpha}$ $\alpha=1.5-1.9$
 - Solar flares with the energy of 10^{32} erg occur once in 10 years.

Fig.1: solar flare

Can "superflares" (flares with $E > 10^{33}$ erg) occur on our Sun?

- Only 9 superflares on solar-type stars were reported before the Kepler era. (Schaefer et al. 2000)
- Small-amplitude (10^{-4} for 10^{32} erg flares)
- Low-frequency (< 1 in 100 years)

Kepler has a capability to detect superflares on solar-type stars.

- High-photometric precision ($\sim 10^{-4}$)
 - comparable to the amplitude of X10-class solar flares
- Large number of targets ($\sim 10^5$ solar-type stars) and continuous observation (~ 4 years)

Fig.2: Frequency distribution of solar flares

2. Kepler data

We searched for superflares on solar-type stars from the Kepler data.

- Long-cadence data (Q0-Q6): 90000 solar-type stars (Maehara et al. 2012, Shibayama et al. 2013) $5100 < T_{\text{eff}} < 6000$; $\log g > 4.0$ (from KIC; Brown et al. 2011)
- Short-cadence data (Q0-Q17): 1547 solar-type stars (Maehara et al. 2015) $5300 < T_{\text{eff}} < 6300$; $\log g > 4.0$ (from Huber et al. 2014)

3. Light curves of superflares

Fig. 3: Light curves of superflares (red: short-cadence data; blue: long-cadence data)

- Long-cadence data: 1547 superflares on 279 solar-type stars.
- Short-cadence data: 189 superflares on 23 solar-type stars.
 - Flare amplitude: $1.3 \times 10^{-3} \sim 8.5 \times 10^{-2}$
 - Bolometric energy: $2 \times 10^{32} \sim 2 \times 10^{36}$ erg

- Most of superflare stars show quasi-periodic brightness modulations.
 - Period: 1 ~ 30 days
 - Amplitude: $10^{-3} \sim 10^{-1}$

→ Superflare stars have large starspots.

Fig.4: Lightcurve (left) and artificial image of a superflare star (right)

4. Flare frequency distribution

Fig.5: Frequency distribution of superflares on solar-type stars

Fig.6: Comparison between occurrence frequency of superflares on Sun-like stars and those of solar flares

Frequency distribution of superflares: power-law distribution ($\alpha=1.5$)

- Similar to the frequency distribution of solar flares ($\alpha=1.5-1.9$)
- Frequency distribution of superflares on Sun-like stars and those of solar flares are roughly on the same power-law line. (Sun-like stars: $5600\text{K} < T_{\text{eff}} < 6300\text{K}$; $P_{\text{rot}} > 10$ days)

Frequency vs. rotation period

- Flare frequency decreases as the rotation period increases ($P_{\text{rot}} > 2-3$ days).

Fig.7 Flare frequency as a function of rotation period.

5. Flare energy

Flare energy would be a fraction of the magnetic energy stored near starspots.

$$E_{\text{flare}} \approx f E_{\text{mag}} \approx f \frac{B^2 L^3}{8\pi} \approx f \frac{B^2}{8\pi} A_{\text{spot}}^{3/2}$$

f : fraction of magnetic energy released by the flare, B : magnetic field strength, L : scale length of the starspot group

- Upper limit of flare energy is comparable to $\sim 10\%$ of the stored magnetic energy.
 - Large starspots (1~10% of solar hemisphere) are necessary to produce superflares.
- Upper limit of flare energy ($10^{35} \sim 10^{36}$ erg) does not depend on the rotation period.
 - Superflares can occur on slowly rotating solar-type stars.

Fig.8: Flare energy vs. area of starspots

Fig.9: Flare energy vs. rotation period

6. Flare duration

- Flare duration (τ) increased as flare energy (E_{flare}) increases.
 - short-cadence data: $\tau \propto E^{0.39 \pm 0.03}$

$$E_{\text{flare}} \propto E_{\text{mag}} \propto L^3 B^2$$

$$\tau \propto \text{Alfvén time scale} \propto L / v_A$$

$$\Rightarrow \tau \propto E_{\text{flare}}^{1/3}$$

Fig. 10: Flare duration vs. flare energy

- Analytical power-law slope for the correlation between duration and energy (1/3) is comparable to the observed value (0.39 ± 0.03).

7. Superflare stars having exoplanets

From the NASA Exoplanet Archive (May 29th, 2016)

	All stars	Stars with confirmed planets	Stars with candidate & confirmed planets
All solar-type stars (Revised KIC: $T_{\text{eff}}=5300-6300\text{K}$, $\log g > 4.0$)	102551	1029 (1.0%)	2131 (2.1%)
Solar-type superflare stars (Shibayama+2013)	279	1 (Kepler-491 b) (0.4%)	3 (1.1%)